

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

RUNNING HEAD: Muscle synergies in adaptation and generalization

Changes in Muscle Synergy Structure and Activation Patterns Underlie Force Field Adaptation, Retention, and Generalization

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Supplemental Fig. S1: Ideal (dashed) and actual exerted (solid) perpendicular force profiles on EC trials during the baseline, adapted state, and the beginning (20 trials) of the delayed retention and generalization phase. Depicted are mean and SDM (shaded) values.

Supplemental Fig. S1: Movement speed across different phases. A single line shows the mean speed-time curve of one participant in the respective phase. Single lines are colored according to the participant's group assignment

Supplemental Fig. S3: Average and SDM trial duration across trials and participants for each phase. The green band shows the time window in which the target turned green upon reaching it. The asterisk denotes a significant difference in trial duration with respect to the adapted state (reference) trial durations, based on the LMM presented in the following. 'Trial Duration ~ DIR_-90_BL + DIR_0_BL + DIR_45_BL + Delayed + (1 | Participant)'. In this model, "DIR_-90_BL", "DIR_0_BL", "DIR_45_BL", and "Delayed" are categorical variables indicating the phase ("BL" for baseline and "Delayed" for the delayed tests) and the direction (numbers) to which the trial belongs. All NF trials toward -90°, 0°, and 45° during baseline, as well as the 20 adapted state FF trials and the first 20 FF trials of the delayed retention and generalization phase, were included. The results are presented in the following table. Note that "Delayed" has been split into the three directions, i.e., groups, in the figure, while it is one fixed factor in the LMM (each participant was assigned to one direction only in the delayed phase).

Supplemental Table S1: Differences in trial duration by direction and phase according to the LMM described in Supplemental Fig. S3.

Fixed effects	β estimate (lower, upper 95% CI)	t	p
(Intercept)	0.61 (0.60, 0.62)	122.27	<0.01*
DIR_-90_BL	-0.01 (-0.02, 0.00)	-1.27	0.203
DIR_0_BL	-0.01 (-0.02, 0.00)	-1.45	0.148
DIR_45_BL	-0.03 (-0.04, -0.02)	-4.31	<0.01*
Delayed	0.01 (-0.00, 0.02)	1.54	0.123
Random effects			
(Intercept)	0.03 (0.02, 0.04)		
Error	0.14 (0.14, 0.15)		